

On the impact of soil texture on local scale organic carbon quantification: From airborne to spaceborne sensing domains

Vahid Khosravi^{a,*}, Asa Gholizadeh^a, Daniel Žížala^{a,b}, Radka Kodešová^a,
 Mohammadmehdi Saberioon^{c,d}, Prince Chapman Agyeman^e, Petra Vokurková^a,
 Anna Juřicová^b, Marko Spasić^a, Luboš Borůvka^a

^a Department of Soil Science and Soil Protection, Faculty of Agrobiolgy, Food and Natural Resources, Czech University of Life Sciences Prague, Kamýcká 129, Suchbát, Prague 16500, Czech Republic

^b Research Institute for Soil and Water Conservation, Žabovřeská 250, Prague 15600, Czech Republic

^c Helmholtz Centre Potsdam GFZ German Research Centre for Geosciences, Section 1.4 Remote Sensing and Geoinformatics, Telegrafenberg, Potsdam 14473, Germany

^d ILVO, Flanders Research Institute for Agriculture, Fisheries and Food, Technology and Food Science-Agricultural Engineering, Merelbeke 9820, Belgium

^e Division of Plant Sciences and Technology, University of Missouri-Columbia, Columbia, MO 65211, USA

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ABSTRACT

Soil organic carbon (SOC) distribution and interaction with light is influenced by soil texture parameters (clay, silt and sand), which makes SOC prediction complicated, especially in samples with considerable pedological variability. Hence, understanding the relationship between SOC and soil texture is important within the context of SOC prediction using remote sensing data. The main objective of this study was to find the impact of soil texture on the performance of local SOC prediction models that were developed on Sentinel-2 (S2) multispectral and CASI/SASI (CS) hyperspectral airborne data as the main predictor variables. One approach to that objective was to lowering the texture variance by stratification of the samples. Therefore, soil samples collected from four agricultural sites in the Czech Republic were segregated based on the i) site-based and ii) texture-based stratification strategies. Random forest (RF) models were then developed on all stratified classes with and without considering the soil texture parameters as predictor variables and results were compared with those obtained by the RF models developed on the non-stratified (NS) samples. Both stratification strategies provided more homogeneous classes, which enhanced the accuracy of SOC prediction, compared to using the NS samples. In addition, the texture-based RF models yielded higher accuracy predictions than the site-based ones. Except sand, adding texture parameters to the main predictors improved accuracy of the models, so that the highest prediction performance was obtained by a texture-based model developed on clay added CS data. Overall, texture-based stratification could significantly enhance the SOC prediction, when the texture parameters were added to the S2 and CS data as the main predictor variables.

1. Introduction

Soil organic carbon (SOC) monitoring is a critical step for sustainable land use practices and alleviating the climate change impacts (Gautam et al., 2022). Traditional SOC quantification methods are precise but require tedious soil sampling campaigns, expensive equipment and hazardous chemicals (Schillaci et al., 2017a). There has thus been a constant demand for rapid and inexpensive alternative techniques to compensate for drawbacks of those methods.

Within recent decades, remote sensing has been capable of quick and

non-destructive monitoring of some specific soil properties, including SOC. Spaceborne multispectral and hyperspectral sensors have shown huge capabilities for broad and continuous coverage of the earth surface and production of soil surface maps even from the inaccessible and hard to reach regions (Biney et al., 2021). As an example, Sentinel-2 (S2) with revisit interval of 5–7 days, provides multispectral optical imagery for high spatial resolution terrestrial observations. Encouraging SOC prediction performances have been obtained using S2 data for temperate soils in the Czech Republic (Gholizadeh et al., 2018; Žížala et al., 2019), Belgium and Germany (Castaldi et al., 2019a) and Northern France

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: khosravi@af.czu.cz (V. Khosravi).

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(Vaudour et al., 2019). The hyperspectral data acquired by the classic spaceborne sensors (e.g., Hyperion) suffer from low spatial and temporal resolution and low signal to noise ratio (SNR) (Gomez et al., 2008). Endeavors have been made to address these shortcomings by the current or forthcoming Earth observation missions such as Environmental Mapping and Analysis Program (EnMAP) (Storch et al., 2023) and Copernicus Hyperspectral Imaging Mission for the Environment (CHIME) (Nieke and Rast, 2018). Successful imaging of SOC has also been reported in several studies that implemented multi- or hyperspectral sensors mounted on aircrafts (Gholizadeh et al., 2018; Hong et al., 2020; Guo et al., 2021; Majeed et al., 2023) or drones (Wehrhan and Sommer, 2021; Biney et al., 2021; 2023). The lower imaging altitude of these aerial platforms has led to higher spatial resolution data and hence more robust prediction models and higher precision and quality distribution maps.

The accuracy of remote sensing - based SOC estimation is usually influenced by factors such as soil texture and moisture (Jiang et al., 2016; Castaldi et al., 2019a), wet and dry vegetation (Dvorakova et al., 2020; Castaldi, 2021) and atmospheric conditions (Dvorakova et al., 2020) which must be taken into account cautiously. The relationship between SOC and soil texture parameters (i.e., clay, silt and sand) is complicated and variable (Stenberg et al., 2010), mainly depending on some factors like soil type, aggregates, land use and management practices. However, there is generally a strong correlation between SOC and finer texture content of soil, such as clay. That is because fine clay particles provide a large surface area with negative charge, allowing them to adsorb SOC and protect it from microbial deterioration and decomposition (Barré et al., 2014; Han et al., 2016; Adiyah et al., 2022). Silt particles also have large surfaces which facilitate the aggregation and retention of SOC, although the SOC and silt have a more complex relationship since silt can be easily lost by wind and water erosion. The relationship between SOC and sand depends on various factors including climate as well as soil type, zone, structure and management practices (Yost and Hartemink, 2019). Generally, soils with coarser textures, such as sand, store lower content of SOC (Yost and Hartemink, 2019). That is mainly due to lower surface area (Almajmaie et al., 2017), water-holding capacity (Šimanský et al., 2019) and nutrient content of sandy soils (Almajmaie et al., 2017; Šimanský et al., 2019), which limit their plant growth capacity and hence organic matter inputs. In addition, sandy soils have more coarse pores which cause better aeration and hence, faster decomposition of their SOC contents.

To overcome the above-mentioned complexity between soil texture parameters and SOC, especially in large datasets, soil samples can be stratified (i.e., divided) into several classes based on a certain feature. Models built on stratified samples have shown improved accuracies of SOC estimation, which is because of lower variability and similar characteristics of each sample group (Wetterlind and Stenberg, 2010; Castaldi et al., 2018). In a study in the United States, texture-based stratification of nearly 20000 nationwide soil samples into more homogeneous groups led to a significant improvement in prediction of SOC using visible–near infrared–shortwave infrared (Vis–NIR–SWIR; 350–2500 nm) reflectance spectra (Wijewardane et al., 2016). On a nation-wide scale study in Germany, some soil properties like texture were used for stratification of samples, which caused an increase in accuracy of SOC model calibrated on the NIR spectra. Separation of the sandy soil samples from the other samples caused a 14% reduction in root mean square error (RMSE) (Jaconi et al., 2017). In another study by Moura-Bueno et al. (2020), the stratification of a soil spectral library (SSL) resulted in higher accuracy of SOC predictions than when using general models. Stratification can also be applied based on regional (Igne et al., 2010) and geological (Udelhoven et al., 2003) characteristics of the dataset. Region-based division of samples led to superior local models with enhanced SOC prediction performances (Wijewardane et al., 2016).

Despite numerous literatures documenting the relationship of texture parameters with SOC (Bosatta and Ågren, 1997; Dexter, 2004;

Wiesmeier et al., 2019; Wang et al., 2021; Johannes et al., 2023), only a few studies have delved into their impact on SOC prediction (Schillaci et al., 2017b; Hamzehpour et al., 2019; Swetha and Chakraborty, 2021; Garosi et al., 2022). Above-mentioned lacuna is more acute, when multi- and hyperspectral imagery are being used as the main SOC predictor variables. To the best of our knowledge, no study has investigated the effect of texture-based stratification on SOC prediction models, developed solely on the image spectra. The main purpose of this study, hence, was to explore the influence of soil texture on performance of the SOC prediction models developed using multi- and hyperspectral remote sensing data. To do so, we stratified the soil samples into different classes based on i) geographical location and ii) soil texture strategies and then examined how well the S2 multispectral and CASI/SASI (CS) airborne hyperspectral imagery, can predict SOC contents within each defined class, either with or without involving the texture parameters as predictor variables.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Study sites, soil sampling and analysis

This study was conducted in four agricultural sites of Nová Ves nad Popelkou (Nová Ves), Jičín, Klučov and Přestavky (Fig. 1), located in rural areas of the Czech Republic. Oilseed rape, spring and winter cereals, potatoes and maize are mostly being cultivated in them. An attempt was made to select homogeneous soilscape representative sites with the same climatic conditions (precipitation and temperature), land management and terrain characteristics (Žizala et al., 2017). Dissected relief with tributary valleys, toe and back slopes and plateaus are some of the main landform features of our study sites.

Soils of the study sites, as described by the World reference base (WRB) for soil resources (IUSS Working Group WRB, 2014), are mostly composed of Cambisols and Stagnosols on crystalline and sedimentary rocks and Chernozems and Luvisols on loess. Details about the sampling sites and data collection campaigns are presented in Table 1.

Overall, 320 soil samples were collected from the topsoil (0–20 cm) of four study sites in June 2021 (80 samples from each). Stratified random strategy conditioned Latin Hypercube Sampling (cLHS) was used for the sampling design. A GeoXM global positioning system (GPS) (Trimble Inc., Sunnyvale, California, USA) with 1 m accuracy was employed to record the position of each sampling point. Soil samples were taken as composite samples, then air-dried, ground, sieved (≤ 2 mm) and thoroughly mixed before analyzing (ISO 11464:2006). SOC was measured using the Walkley–Black method. Soil texture (i.e., clay, silt and sand) content of the samples was determined by the analysis of particle size distribution (less than 0.002 mm, 0.002–0.01 mm, 0.01–0.05 mm, 0.05–0.25 mm and 0.25–2 mm fractions) using the pipette method (ISO 11277:2009).

2.2. Airborne hyperspectral imaging, data pre-processing and co-registration

The airborne hyperspectral imaging campaign was carried out on June 3rd, 2021, at least five days after the last rain. Data acquisition took place using Vis–NIR (380–1050 nm) CASI (Itres Ltd., Calgary, Canada) and shortwave infrared (SWIR; 950–2450 nm) SASI (Itres Ltd., Calgary, Canada) sensors (Table 2), aboard Cessna 208B Grand Caravan photogrammetric aircraft. A ground survey was also carried out, on the day of the campaign, to obtain information on soil cover of vegetation and plant residues, moisture and surface roughness.

Data pre-processing (radiometric and geometric corrections) were performed by Global Change Research Institute of the Czech Academy of Sciences, via flying laboratory of imaging systems (FLIS). Radiometric corrections were done in the RadCorr Ver. 9.3.6.0 (Itres Ltd., Calgary, Canada) using laboratory determined calibration parameters. The basic procedure of radiometric correction consisted of the dark subtraction

Fig. 1. Distribution of study sites in the a) Czech Republic and sampling fields in b) Klučov, c) Prestavlky, d) Nová Ves nad Popelkou and e) Jičín.

Table 1
Study sites, soil sampling and imaging campaign specifications.

Site	Area (ha)	Dominant soil unit	Parent material	Soil sampling date	Airborne data acquisition date	Sentinel-2 data acquisition date
Nová Ves	129	Eutric Cambisol	Permian-Carboniferous rocks (sandstone, siltstone)	June, 2021	03.06.2021	04.06.2021
Jičín	153	Luvisol, Albic Luvisol, Luvic Chernozem	Pleistocene loess	June, 2021	03.06.2021	04.06.2021
Klučov	175	Calcic Chernozem, Luvic Chernozem, Regosols	Pleistocene loess, Cretaceous marl, terrace gravels	June, 2021	03.06.2021	19.06.2021
Přestavlky	58	Haplic Stagnosol, Eutric and Stagnic Cambisol, Leptosol	Complex of Proterozoic and Paleozoic rocks (schist, granodiorite)	June, 2021	03.06.2021	19.06.2021

Table 2
CASI and SASI sensors specifications.

Sensor	Number of bands	Spectral range (nm)	Spectral resolution (nm)	Field of view (FOV)	FWHM (nm)
CASI	72	Vis-NIR, 380–1050	3.2	40°	10
SASI	100	SWIR, 950–2450	15	40°	15

and conversion of raw values taken by the sensor (DN: digital numbers) into physically defined radiance units. Atmospheric corrections were implemented using the MODerate resolution atmospheric TRANsmission (MODTRAN) radiative transfer model (RTM) incorporated in the ATCOR-4 Ver. 7.3 (ReSe Applications Schlapfler Inc., Wil, Switzerland). The resulting atmospherically corrected data were expressed as reflectance at the surface level values. Geometric corrections, orthorectification and georeferencing (UTM zone 33 N, ETRS-89) of data were carried out using data collected by the GNSS/IMU sensor and the digital elevation model (DEM) in the GeoCor Ver. 3.7.2 (Itres

Ltd., Calgary, Canada). The noisy bands at the two edges of the sensors' spectra were eliminated, resulted in 64 (from 383.05 to 981.98 nm) and 98 (from 987.5 to 2442.5 nm) remaining bands for CASI and SASI sensors, respectively. Before the main processing step, the CASI data were resampled to the spatial resolution of the SASI sensor (6 m). Data fusion was then performed to merge the CASI and SASI imagery into one hyperspectral full Vis-NIR-SWIR spectral range data cube. Afterwards, reflectance (R) was transformed to absorbance via $\log(1/R)$ and the first derivative (FD) transformation was applied on the spectra to remove the baseline offset (Gholizadeh et al., 2015; Khosravi et al., 2020).

2.3. Multispectral satellite data pre-processing and indices retrieval

The two cloud-free bottom of atmosphere (BOA) Sentinel-2 level-2A (S2) images were downloaded from the Copernicus open access hub as close as possible to the sampling campaign date (Table 1). Since the downloaded S2 products were geometrically and atmospherically corrected, there was no need for pre-processing of the downloaded images. The six 20 m-pixel bands were resampled to 10 m to obtain a finer pixel size S2 image and hence more precise selection of the bare soil pixels and draw better comparison with the 6 m resolution CS data. S2 related

variables including ten bands and 19 spectral indices were extracted and calculated at each sampling point and employed as covariates to develop the SOC prediction models. A Pearson correlation analysis was conducted to explore the possible autocorrelations between the input indices and consequent adverse effects such as increasing the calibration complexity and reduction in accuracy of the SOC estimations. According to the results, there were significant correlations between some indices such as NDVI and TVI, WdVI and V, BI2 and TSAVI, and EVI and SAVI. Some combinations of the indices were used as inputs to investigate their effects on the prediction. Considering the negligible differences observed between the results, all indices were incorporated in calibration of the SOC models to employ the maximum number of S2 related covariates. The S2 bands' details and equations of the indices can be found in Table A1 and Table A2, respectively.

2.4. Selection of bare soil pixels

The normalized difference vegetation index (NDVI) and normalized burn ratio 2 (NBR2) (Table A2) indices have been considerably used to delineate green vegetation (Huang et al., 2021) and crop residues (Dvorakova et al., 2023), respectively. Although the sensitivity of NBR2 to detect crop residues on wet soils is very limited, they form a linear relationship for dry soils (Dvorakova et al., 2021), like the case in this study. Accordingly, both NDVI and NBR2 indices were implemented for both S2 and CS to remove the pixels with green and dry vegetation and crop residue cover. The NDVI threshold was determined by visual inspection of the true color composite (TCC) of S2 (R: 664.6 nm, G: 559.8 nm and B: 492.4 nm) and airborne (R: 658.8 nm, G: 554.2 nm and B: 478.1 nm) images. Various NBR2 threshold values ranging from 0.05 to 0.25, with increment of 0.01 were selected and tested to isolate the bare soil areas. Results were validated by comparing the retrieved pixels with field-based ground truth observations.

2.5. Sample stratification and correlation analysis

The samples corresponding to the remaining bare soil areas were stratified based on the study sites and the United States Department of Agriculture (USDA) texture triangle. The texture triangle of the USDA is one of the most popular systems of soil classification, evolved from eight classes right-angled triangle (Whitney, 1911) and ten classes equilateral triangle (Davis, 1927) models to a twelve groups final version introduced in 1951, which is currently in effect (USDA, 1951, 2017).

The Pearson correlation between SOC and each texture parameter was calculated within each stratified class to provide an insight into their relationship, while investigating the possible impacts of interaction between the two variables on SOC prediction.

2.6. SOC modeling and performance assessment

For each stratified class, random forest (RF) algorithm (Breiman, 2001) was used to develop the prediction models using S2 and CS imagery, with and without separate and combined incorporation of the texture parameters as additional predictor variables. Results were then compared with those obtained by the RF models calibrated on non-stratified (NS) samples (i.e., on the whole dataset). Three specific parameters used for the RF models in this study were: i) the number of trees in the forest (n_{tree}), ii) quantity of variables used for each tree (m_{try}), and iii) the minimum data per node (nodesize). A grid search was conducted to determine the optimum quantities for the parameters and the value of 500 was obtained for n_{tree} . One third of the total number of predictor variables was the optimal quantity of the m_{try} while the nodesize was set to 5. The 'randomForest' package in RStudio environment (R Core Team, 2020) was used to run the RF model. Using variable importance in projection (VIP), the contribution of all input predictor variables, including the texture parameters, were assessed on outcome of each developed class-model. This can help to determine the extent to

which the texture can influence the prediction accuracy.

To develop the models, samples were divided into training and testing (75:25% ratio) datasets, using the Kennard–Stone (KS) algorithm, which chooses representative samples based on a distance measure (Kennard and Stone, 1969). A 5-fold cross-validation technique was used to calibrate the SOC prediction models on the training dataset. The two most common evaluation criteria, RMSE and coefficient of determination (R^2) (Eq. 1 and Eq. 2, respectively) were selected to assess performance of the developed models.

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (o_i - p_i)^2} \quad (1)$$

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (o_i - p_i)^2}{\sum_{i=1}^n (o_i - \mu_o)^2} \quad (2)$$

where, n is the number of samples, μ_o is the mean for the observed values and o_i and p_i are the observed and predicted values, respectively. A robust model, generally, has high R^2 and low RMSE. A flowchart of the methodology is provided in Fig. 2.

3. Results

3.1. General statistics and correlations

After rigorous perusal, pixels with NDVI values below 0.23 were kept for both satellite and airborne images. Different models were then developed on the samples remaining after applying various NBR2 thresholds (from 0.05 to 0.25 with increment of 0.01) and the optimal value of 0.09 was obtained. By applying the optimal NDVI and NBR2 thresholds, 200 bare soil pixels/samples which were fully compatible between the two datasets were finally retrieved and used for the rest of the study.

Fig. 3 and Fig. 4 show the statistics, histograms and the remaining soil samples (based on the USDA texture triangles), for the site-based and texture-based stratified samples, respectively. The statistics of NS samples have also been shown in Fig. 3. According to the results, SOC contents of the NS samples ranged from the minimum value of 0.31% to the maximum value of 2.59% with average and coefficient of variation (CV) of 1.19% and 0.27, respectively. Among the study sites, SOC in Klučov had the highest CV of 0.29 followed by Přestavky (CV = 0.24) and Nová Ves (CV = 0.22), respectively. The highest CV of clay and silt were observed in Přestavky, while Klučov showed the highest CV of sand. That was while Jičín indicated the lowest CV values for all three texture parameters. According to the histogram plots and related distribution curves, SOC contents of all classes almost followed the normal distribution. Other variables did not follow a certain distribution in different classes (Fig. 3).

According to the USDA texture triangle (Fig. 4), samples were mostly plotted in lower positioned classes of sandy loam (SL), loam (L), silt loam (SiL), silty clay loam (SiCL) and clay loam (CL). For this reason, samples were stratified into four groups of SL with 46 samples, L with 59 samples, SiL with 51 samples and SiCL_CL as combination of SiCL and CL with 44 samples (Fig. 4). Accordingly, the SiCL_CL and SiL classes had higher amounts of clay and silt, class L had relatively equal quantities of sand and silt and the SL class included samples with high sand contents. Considering the SOC level in each texture class, the SiCL_CL had the highest average of SOC (1.23%) with highest CV of 0.31. SiL and SL classes had the lowest SOC content with averages of 1.15% and 1.17%, respectively. According to the distributions of soil textures within the USDA texture triangle, most of Nová Ves, Jičín, Klučov and Přestavky samples were in loam, silt loam, silty clay loam and loam classes, respectively (Fig. 4).

The Pearson correlation coefficients between SOC and clay, silt and sand in the NS and stratified classes are presented in Table 3. None of the

Fig. 2. Flowchart of the study.

texture parameters showed significant correlation with SOC in the NS class. Regarding the site-based stratified classes, SOC showed significant correlation with all texture parameters in Nová Ves, Klučov and Přestavlký sites. In addition, the interrelationship was positive between SOC and clay as well as SOC and silt and negative between SOC and sand within those study sites. The highest positive correlation of SOC was observed with clay in Klučov ($r = 0.84$, $P < 0.001$), while the highest negative correlation was detected between SOC and sand for Přestavlký ($r = -0.39$, $P < 0.001$). No significant correlations were observed between SOC and texture parameters in Jičín.

Considering the texture-based stratified classes, SOC was positively correlated with the clay content, while the correlation between SOC and sand was negative in all classes excluding L. Though not quite strong, the

highest negative correlation between SOC and sand content was in SL class ($r = -0.32$, $p\text{-value} < 0.05$), while SOC and clay showed the highest positive correlation in SiCL_CL ($r = 0.75$, $p\text{-value} < 0.05$).

3.2. Modeling results

3.2.1. General comparison

Tables A3 and 4 display the SOC prediction results for the models created on the NS, site- and texture-based stratified samples (calibration and validation sets, respectively). Fig. 5 and Fig. A1 also show the scatterplots of the best models obtained for each strategy and stratified class on the S2 + clay and CS + clay datasets, respectively. Prediction results of models developed on NS samples are likewise shown. As can be

Fig. 3. Histograms and summary statistics of SOC (first column), clay (second column), silt (third column) and sand (fourth column) within all stratified and non-stratified classes (NS: non-stratified, SL: Sandy Loam, L: Loam, SiL: Silt Loam, SiCL_CL: combination of SiCL (Silty Clay Loam) and CL (Clay Loam)).

Fig. 3. (continued).

observed, the models developed on the CS outperformed those developed on the S2 data. This superiority was more evident (up to 60%) in the models developed on NS samples (Table 4, Fig. 5 and Fig. A1).

Even though fewer samples were used for modeling, models developed on the stratified samples indicated better performance than those developed on the NS samples. As an example, the site-based stratification caused a minimum improvement of 7%, when using the CS data as the main predictor variable (+ clay, silt and sand). This improvement was more pronounced (at least 29%), when the S2 image was considered as the main predictor variable (+ clay, silt and sand). The lowest model performances among all (RMSE > 0.17% and R² < 0.41), linked to those developed on the NS samples, regardless of the employed data type and predictor variables.

Comparing the results obtained under the site- and texture-based stratification strategies, the models developed on SiCL_CL and SiL

outperformed all the site-based stratified ones, showing that dividing samples based on their texture parameters can lead to more successful SOC predictions. This conclusion holds true, except for some models developed on the classes with higher sand content, especially SL, which performed very poorly (RMSE > 0.16% and R² < 0.42). In other words, the models developed for Klučov and Přestavky, under the site-based stratification, had higher performances than the L and SL models, developed under the texture-based stratification. The performance of some models developed for Jičín was also similar to those developed on the L class (like the model developed on the CS data +clay with RMSE = 0.13% and R² = 0.60).

Among all the texture parameters, adding clay as the predictor variable caused the highest enhancement in performance of the models. The best improvement was obtained for Jičín, where incorporation of clay enhanced the prediction performance up to 30% compared to the

Fig. 4. USDA texture triangles for the non-stratified, site- and texture-based stratified soil classes (NS: non-stratified, SL: Sandy Loam, L: Loam, SiL: Silt Loam, SiCL_CL: combination of SiCL (Silty Clay Loam) and CL (Clay Loam)).

situations that no texture parameter added as the input variable. Adding all texture parameters together also made substantial improvements compared to when the multi- or hyperspectral data were used as the only predictors. Adding silt and sand individually, on the other hand, did not introduce any improvement to the models' prediction performances. It is noteworthy to mention that adding the texture parameters caused more improvement for the models developed on the site-based stratified samples than those developed on the texture-based stratified ones. Furthermore, adding texture parameters caused an average higher performance of 4.73% for the models developed using the S2 data, while the average enhancement was 3.78% considering the CS data as the main predictor.

3.2.2. Site-based stratification

Considering Table 4, Přestavky and Klučov yielded acceptable SOC prediction performances on both S2 and airborne data. However, the best results under the site-based stratification strategy were obtained on the airborne hyperspectral data + clay with RMSE = 0.11% and $R^2 = 0.71$, followed by the airborne hyperspectral data + clay + silt + sand with RMSE = 0.12% and $R^2 = 0.70$, both for the Klučov site. Likewise, for the Přestavky site, the models developed on the airborne hyperspectral data + clay (RMSE = 0.12% and $R^2 = 0.65$) and the airborne hyperspectral data + clay + silt + sand (RMSE = 0.12% and $R^2 = 0.63$) showed the highest performances.

The same trend was observed for the models developed using S2 (with and without the texture parameters) dataset. Accordingly, Klučov

Table 3

Correlation matrix between SOC content and soil texture parameters in the non-stratified and stratified soil classes.

Correlation coefficient					
Texture parameter	NS	Nová Ves	Jičín	Klučov	Přestavky
Clay	0.05	0.46*	0.19	0.84**	0.48**
Silt	-0.10	0.41**	-0.08	0.73*	0.60***
Sand	0.05	-0.22	0.10	-0.23**	-0.39***
Texture parameter	SL	L	SiL	SiCL_CL	
Clay	0.60*	0.22*	0.30**	0.75*	
Silt	0.50***	-0.10	0.36**	-0.40**	
Sand	-0.32*	0.05	-0.04	-0.01	

NS: non-stratified, SL: sandy loam, L: loam, SiL: silt loam, SiCL_CL: combination of silty clay loam (SiCL) and clay loam (CL).

*, ** and *** indicate significance at $P < 0.05$, $P < 0.01$ and $P < 0.001$, respectively.

and Přestavky had relatively acceptable predictions, especially when texture parameters were incorporated as the predictor variables (S2 + clay with RMSE = 0.13% and $R^2 = 0.64$, S2 + clay + silt + sand with RMSE = 0.13% and $R^2 = 0.59$, for Klučov, and S2 + clay with RMSE = 0.15% and $R^2 = 0.61$ and S2 + clay + silt + sand with RMSE = 0.14% and $R^2 = 0.58$, for Přestavky). For other sites (Nová Ves and Jičín), the performance of site-based stratification models dropped, regardless of using S2 or airborne datasets. For example, the best model for Jičín and Nová Ves was developed using airborne hyperspectral data + clay with RMSE = 0.13% and $R^2 = 0.60$ and RMSE = 0.16% and $R^2 = 0.46$, respectively.

3.2.3. Texture-based stratification

Among all models developed on the texture-based stratified samples, those developed on the SiCL_CL samples showed the highest prediction performances, followed by the SiL models (Table 4). This was regardless of the type of data and the texture parameters added as input predictor variables. The best prediction accuracy was obtained for the SiCL_CL class model developed on the airborne hyperspectral data + clay (RMSE = 0.08% and $R^2 = 0.81$), followed by the same class model developed on the airborne hyperspectral data + clay + silt + sand (RMSE = 0.10% and $R^2 = 0.78$). According to Table 4, it is highlighted that the SiCL_CL models also yielded promising results including RMSE = 0.10% and $R^2 = 0.78$ for the airborne hyperspectral data + clay and RMSE = 0.10% and $R^2 = 0.73$ for the airborne hyperspectral data + clay + silt + sand. Contrarily, performance of models developed on the L (RMSE = 0.12% and $R^2 = 0.62$) and SL (RMSE = 0.16% and $R^2 = 0.42$) classes was not reasonable.

3.2.4. Variable importance

Variable importance plots of the RF models developed on different classes of samples are shown in Fig. 6. Accordingly, the 30 highest influential predictor variables of each model are presented along with their percentage increase in mean squared error (%IncMSE) as a measure of variable importance obtained during the calibration of the models. As evidenced, clay was amongst the top important variables in almost all models (excluding Nová Ves CS). It also made the largest contribution to the accuracy of the model developed on SiCL_CL class with %IncMSE of 3.48 for the CS dataset. Compared to sand, silt better contributed to development of the models, especially when combined with the CS data. The most significant impact of sand was on the models developed for SL and Přestavky classes (Fig. 6).

4. Discussion

4.1. SOC prediction: effect of correlation with the texture parameters

It has generally been proved that SOC content is positively and negatively related to clay and sand contents of soil, respectively (Song

Table 4 SOC prediction results of the RF models developed on the non-stratified and stratified classes of samples (validation dataset).

Data type	Texture input variable	NS (200 samples)		Nová Ves (60 samples)		Jičín (18 samples)		Klučov (59 samples)		Přestavky (63 samples)		SL (46 samples)		L (59 samples)		SiL (51 samples)		SiCL_CL (44 samples)	
		RMSE	R ²	RMSE	R ²	RMSE	R ²	RMSE	R ²	RMSE	R ²	RMSE	R ²	RMSE	R ²	RMSE	R ²	RMSE	R ²
Sentinel-2	None	0.27	0.24	0.28	0.32	0.19	0.43	0.16	0.55	0.17	0.55	0.28	0.24	0.17	0.48	0.13	0.56	0.13	0.59
	All	0.26	0.26	0.27	0.34	0.14	0.55	0.13	0.59	0.14	0.58	0.25	0.25	0.13	0.55	0.11	0.59	0.11	0.63
	Clay	0.26	0.27	0.27	0.35	0.15	0.56	0.13	0.64	0.15	0.61	0.26	0.24	0.12	0.57	0.11	0.61	0.10	0.66
	Silt	0.27	0.24	0.27	0.32	0.18	0.42	0.16	0.55	0.17	0.54	0.28	0.23	0.16	0.48	0.13	0.57	0.13	0.60
CS	Sand	0.27	0.23	0.28	0.31	0.21	0.41	0.15	0.57	0.18	0.55	0.27	0.23	0.18	0.44	0.15	0.56	0.14	0.55
	None	0.19	0.38	0.18	0.43	0.16	0.53	0.14	0.68	0.14	0.60	0.19	0.36	0.16	0.55	0.12	0.69	0.12	0.76
	All	0.17	0.41	0.16	0.44	0.13	0.59	0.12	0.70	0.12	0.63	0.17	0.37	0.12	0.62	0.10	0.73	0.10	0.78
	Clay	0.18	0.41	0.16	0.46	0.13	0.60	0.11	0.71	0.12	0.65	0.16	0.42	0.13	0.60	0.10	0.78	0.08	0.81
	Silt	0.19	0.38	0.20	0.43	0.15	0.53	0.13	0.67	0.15	0.62	0.18	0.36	0.14	0.58	0.13	0.71	0.11	0.76
	Sand	0.23	0.37	0.21	0.41	0.15	0.52	0.15	0.63	0.12	0.67	0.18	0.34	0.15	0.55	0.13	0.69	0.12	0.75

NS: non-stratified, SL: sandy loam, L: loam, SiL: silt loam, SiCL_CL: combination of silty clay loam (SiCL) and clay loam (CL).

Fig. 5. Scatterplots comparing the performance of the best models developed under different stratification strategies: a) non-stratified model on S2 + clay, b) site-based (Klučov) model on S2 + clay, c) texture-based (SiCL_CL) model on S2 + clay, d) non-stratified model on CS + clay, e) site-based (Klučov) model on CS + clay, f) texture-based (SiCL_CL) model on CS + clay.

et al., 2022). Similar patterns were observed in this study (Table 3). The main reason for the significant positive correlation between the clay and SOC contents within most of the classes can be attributed to the high activity of clay particles caused by large number of surface functional groups (Kennedy et al., 2002), which creates a favorable micro-environment to absorb and stabilize SOC and other charged ions and molecules (Chivenge et al., 2011; Jindaluang et al., 2013; Moura-Bueno et al., 2020). Physical entrapment of SOC in clay-mineral aggregates protect SOC from decomposition (Hong et al., 2019). This correlation was higher for the SiCL_CL and Klučov classes (Table 3) mainly due to their higher average contents of both SOC and clay. Same correlation behavior has also been observed between SOC and clay in other studies (Konen et al., 2003; Leifeld et al., 2005; Gholizadeh et al., 2018; Juřicová et al., 2022). Conversely, the correlation between SOC and sand was negative and weak in most of the classes that mainly attributed to the low surface area and large pore spaces of the coarse texture parameters, which cause rapid water drainage and microbial respiration (Adhikari and Hartemink, 2017; Hamzehpour et al., 2019). This, in turn, leads to faster SOC decomposition and lower levels of SOC in sandy soils (Chenu and Plante, 2006; Adhikari and Hartemink, 2017).

Some researchers, on the other hand, have reported lower correlation between SOC and clay (Sollins et al., 1996). For instance, no significant correlation was found between neither clay nor silt contents with SOC in western Oregon forests (Homann et al., 1995) and Spain (Hontoria et al., 1999), where the high heterogeneity of parent materials was considered as the probable obscure on the texture impact on SOC content. Despite the good relationship between SOC and clay in local areas in China, Pan et al. (2003) reported that maximum 30% of the SOC variability can be explained by clay at larger scales like provinces or countries. In another Chinese national scale study on 1546 typical

cropland soil profiles, weak correlation was reported between clay content and SOC (Wang et al., 2005). Effects of other parameters such as climate factors (temperature, precipitation, evapotranspiration), soil moisture and water-holding capacity, land use, altitude and slope gradient were considered as the main reason for low correlation between soil texture parameters and SOC, especially in larger scale studies (Pan et al., 2003; Wang et al., 2005).

It should be noted that correlation does not guarantee causation in predictions. Even if there is no significant correlation between variables, they can still contribute to the prediction of each other, especially when they are used along with other predictors (McLauchlan, 2006; Gojts and van Wesemael, 2007). One important reason for the lack of significant correlation may be due to noise or outliers within the dataset (Bao et al., 2020), or complex/nonlinear relationship between the variables (Liu et al., 2014), which may need advanced modeling methods to unravel. Hence, correlation analysis is just an approach to detect the interactions between SOC and soil texture parameters to find the impact of predictor variables on prediction accuracy.

4.2. SOC prediction: effect of different data inputs

The more accurate SOC prediction by the CS image compared to the S2 data (Table 4) can be due to its higher spatial resolution, which means more captured SOC and other soil parameters variation within the studied sites. Additionally, the lower altitude of the airborne data acquisition leads to higher quality images with less atmospheric interference. Moreover, the CS airborne data includes more wavelengths relevant to specific soil traits, which make them more beneficial than the S2 data with wider bands spectra. The purity of the pixels and instrumental noise can be additional reasons (Gomez et al., 2018). Similar

Fig. 6. Variable importance plots of the RF models developed on different classes of samples (NS: non-stratified, SL: Sandy Loam, L: Loam, SIL: Silt Loam, SiCL_CL: combination of SiCL (Silty Clay Loam) and CL (Clay Loam)).

superiority has also been reported by [Castaldi et al. \(2019b\)](#) in a study on the capability of S2 multispectral and airborne hyperspectral remote sensing data for SOC prediction in croplands in Belgium, Germany and Luxembourg.

Adding all texture parameters may be advantageous when the interactions between SOC and soil texture are complex. This probably adds more useful information and therefore helps the model to capture these interactions, limit the confounding impacts of other variables and improve the prediction accuracy. Incorporation of all parameters may, however, cause overfitting in case the modeling becomes too complicated and captures noise other than informative relationships. Adding a single texture variable may be more effective in this condition because it captures the most important SOC information and hence, enhances the prediction performance. Regarding this study, the strong impact of clay on SOC is likely the main reason of its highest importance as the predictor variable. Compared to sand and silt, clay has higher surface area, cation exchange and water holding capacity, emphasizing its importance in binding and retaining SOC ([Chi et al., 2022](#); [Das et al., 2022](#)). Better predictions of SOC when adding clay as a predictor variable ([Table 4](#)) may also be associated with their strong spatial relationship. Using sand or silt separately as a predictor variable was not enough to capture the interactions between SOC and soil texture contents, therefore, no improvement was observed in SOC prediction accuracy ([Table 4](#)). The main reason can be larger size of sand and silt particles than clay, which limits their surface area, cation exchange capacity and SOC binding potential ([Thuriès et al., 2001](#); [Azadia and Shakeri, 2021](#)).

4.3. SOC prediction: effect of different stratification strategies

In this study, the results obtained by the models developed on the stratified samples were better than those obtained by the models developed on the NS samples ([Table 4](#)). The reason is that stratification helps to account for the existing data variability ([Moura-Bueno et al., 2020](#)) caused by factors such as management practices, climate, topography, soil type and texture and spatial dependence on the landscape. Stratification of samples decreases the noise and variability within the dataset, creates more homogeneous groups and boosts the model's ability to identify relationships and patterns between the predictor and response variables ([Costa et al., 2022](#)). It is also likely that the RF model is affected by overfitting caused by learning the noise rather than genuine relationships between SOC and the predictors. However, in this study, stratification of samples has reduced the overfitting risk of the RF model and helped to provide more accurate predictions. Similar SOC prediction improvements have been experienced following stratification of Brazilian subtropical soil spectral library ([Moura-Bueno et al., 2020](#)).

Results obtained by the models developed on the texture-based stratified samples were better than those obtained by the site-based stratification ([Table 4](#)). Soil texture plays an important role in SOC storage and availability to microorganisms and plants, within the soil profile ([Feiziene et al., 2018](#); [Maurya et al., 2020](#)). Texture-based stratification of samples can thus assist the models with more relevant information to capture the distribution and accessibility of SOC. On the other hand, the relatively lower performance of models developed on the site-based stratification can mostly be due to the differences in soil type, texture and environmental conditions which harden finding of the meaningful patterns.

Comparison between the models developed for classes revealed the superiority of Klučov and Přestavky sites in the site-based strategy ([Table 4](#)), which may be due to their high mean contents of SOC and clay. Similar justification can be made regarding the dominance of the SiCL_CL class models within the texture-based strategy. Despite the small sample size in Jičín site, the developed models were also relatively acceptable, compared to those calibrated on the NS and Nová Ves. This can be probably because they all belong to only one texture class of SiL.

It should be noticed that before deciding about a proper stratification strategy, it is important to consider the available data and underlying soil processes, which influence SOC dynamics. In addition, depending on the context and goal of the study, considerable caution should be exercised when forming a final opinion on the superiority of stratified-based models, as both site-based and texture-based stratifications can be helpful in successful prediction of SOC.

5. Conclusions

This study tested whether including soil texture parameters (clay, silt and sand) to S2 multispectral or CS hyperspectral imaging data can improve the accuracy of farm scale SOC prediction models. According to the results, stratification of samples –under both site-based and texture-based strategies– led to more significant correlations between SOC and texture parameters within each of the stratified classes. Stratification also improved the performance of the SOC prediction models, particularly those developed on the texture-based stratified samples. Adding clay to the other input variables caused the highest enhancement in prediction of SOC, regardless of whether the NS samples or any stratified class of samples were used for modeling. All improvements mentioned above were more pronounced when CS airborne data was employed as the main predictor variable. Comparison between the models constructed within each of the stratification strategies revealed the superiority of those with higher clay and/or silt contents (Klučov under the site-based and SiCL_CL under texture-based strategies). Overall, soil texture parameters showed to be highly influential on the performance of SOC prediction models, especially when were added to the S2 and CS imaging spectra as input variables.

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CRedit authorship contribution statement

Radka Kodešová: Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Daniel Žížala:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Data curation. **Luboš Borůvka:** Writing – review & editing, Resources, Project administration, Data curation. **Asa Gholizadeh:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Vahid Khosravi:** Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Petra Vokurková:** Methodology. **Prince Chapman Agyeman:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Software. **Marko Spasić:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology. **Anna Juricová:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Data curation. **Mohammadmehdi Saberioon:** Writing – review & editing, Validation.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Scatterplots comparing the performance of the best models developed for each stratified class on the S2 + clay and CS + clay datasets (NS: non-stratified, SL: Sandy Loam, L: Loam, SIL: Silt Loam, SiCL_CL: combination of SiCL (Silty Clay Loam) and CL (Clay Loam)).

Table A1
Sentinel-2 bands specifications.

Band	Band description	Wavelength range (nm)	Central wavelength (nm)	Spatial resolution (m)
Band 1	Coastal aerosol	433–453	443	60
Band 2	Blue	458–523	490	10
Band 3	Green	543–578	560	10
Band 4	Red	650–680	665	10
Band 5	Vegetation red edge	698–713	705	20
Band 6	Vegetation red edge	733–748	740	20
Band 7	Vegetation red edge	773–793	783	20
Band 8	NIR	785–900	842	10
Band 8 A	Vegetation red edge	855–875	865	20
Band 9	Water vapor	935–955	940	60
Band 10	SWIR - Cirrus	1360–1390	1375	60
Band 11	SWIR	1565–1655	1610	20
Band 12	SWIR	2100–2280	2190	20

NIR: Near Infrared.

Table A2
Sentinel-2 derived indices.

Index	Definition	Details
BI	$\frac{\sqrt{(\rho_{Red} \times \rho_{Red}) + (\rho_{Green} \times \rho_{Green})}}{2}$	
BI2	$\frac{\sqrt{(\rho_{Red} \times \rho_{Red}) + (\rho_{Green} \times \rho_{Green}) + \rho_{NIR} \times \rho_{NIR}}}{3}$	
CI	$\frac{\rho_{Red} - \rho_{Green}}{\rho_{Red} + \rho_{Green}}$	
EVI	$G \frac{\rho_{NIR} - \rho_{Red}}{\rho_{NIR} + C1 \times \rho_{Red} - C2 \times \rho_{Blue} + L}$	G=2.5, C1=6, C2=7.5, L=1
GNDVI	$\frac{\rho_{NIR} - \rho_{Green}}{\rho_{NIR} + \rho_{Green}}$	
GRVI	$\frac{\rho_{Green} - \rho_{Red}}{\rho_{Green} + \rho_{Red}}$	
LSWI	$\frac{\rho_{NIR} - \rho_{SWIR1}}{\rho_{NIR} + \rho_{SWIR1}}$	
MSAVI	$\frac{(1 + L)(\rho_{NIR} - \rho_{Red})}{(\rho_{NIR} + \rho_{Red} + L)}$	L = 1-2 × s × NDVI × WDV
MSAVI2	$2 \times \rho_{NIR} + 1 - \frac{\sqrt{(2 \times \rho_{NIR} + 1)^2 - 8 \times (\rho_{NIR} - \rho_{Red})}}{2}$	
MSI	$\frac{\rho_{SWIR1}}{\rho_{NIR}}$	
NBR2	$\frac{\rho_{SWIR1} - \rho_{SWIR2}}{\rho_{SWIR1} + \rho_{SWIR2}}$	
NDVI	$\frac{\rho_{NIR} - \rho_{Red}}{\rho_{NIR} + \rho_{Red}}$	
RI	$\frac{\rho_{Red} \times \rho_{Red}}{\rho_{Green} \times \rho_{Green} + \rho_{Green}}$	
SATVI	$\frac{\rho_{SWIR1} \times \rho_{Red}}{\rho_{SWIR1} \times \rho_{Red} + L}$	L=1
SAVI	$\frac{(\rho_{NIR} - \rho_{Red}) \times (1 + L)}{\rho_{NIR} - \rho_{Red} + L}$	L=0.5
TVI	$\left(\frac{\rho_{NIR} - \rho_{Red}}{\rho_{NIR} + \rho_{Red}} + 0.5 \right)^{1/2} \times 100$	
TSAVI	$\frac{s(\rho_{NIR} - s \times \rho_{Red} - a)}{(a \times \rho_{NIR} + \rho_{Red} - a \times s + X \times (1 + s \times s))}$	a = Soil line intercept, s = Soil line slope, X = Adjustment factor to minimize soil noise
WDVI	$\rho_{NIR} - C \times \rho_{Red}$	C = $\frac{\rho_{NIR}}{\rho_{Red}}$
V	$\frac{\rho_{NIR}}{\rho_{Red}}$	

BI: Brightness Index, BI2: Second Brightness Index, CI: Color Index, EVI: Enhanced Vegetation Index, GNDVI: Green Normalized Difference Vegetation Index, GRVI: Green-Red Vegetation Index, LSWI: Land Surface Water Index, MSAVI: Modified Soil Adjusted Vegetation Index, MSAVI2: Second Modified Soil Adjusted Vegetation Index, MSI: Moisture Stress Index, NBR2: Normalized Burn Ratio 2, NDVI: Normalized Differences Vegetation Index, RI: Redness Index, SATVI: Soil Adjusted Total Vegetation Index, SAVI: Soil Adjusted Vegetation Index, TVI: Transformed Vegetation Index, TSAVI: Transformed Soil Adjusted Vegetation Index, WDV: Weighted Difference Vegetation Index, V: Vegetation.

Table A3

SOC prediction results of the RF models developed on the non-stratified and stratified classes of samples (calibration dataset).

Data type	Texture input variable	NS (200 samples)		Nová Ves (60 samples)		Jičín (18 samples)		Klučov (59 samples)		Prestavlký (63 samples)		SL (46 samples)		L (59 samples)		SiL (51 samples)		SiCL_CL (44 samples)	
		RMSE	R ²	RMSE	R ²	RMSE	R ²	RMSE	R ²	RMSE	R ²	RMSE	R ²	RMSE	R ²	RMSE	R ²	RMSE	R ²
Sentinel-2	None	0.23	0.27	0.23	0.34	0.15	0.56	0.13	0.61	0.13	0.60	0.23	0.26	0.16	0.55	0.11	0.57	0.13	0.66
	All	0.22	0.31	0.21	0.37	0.12	0.63	0.10	0.66	0.11	0.64	0.22	0.33	0.11	0.58	0.08	0.63	0.10	0.69
	Clay	0.21	0.35	0.21	0.39	0.12	0.61	0.10	0.69	0.11	0.67	0.20	0.33	0.11	0.60	0.09	0.65	0.08	0.72
	Silt	0.22	0.29	0.23	0.36	0.16	0.58	0.13	0.62	0.10	0.63	0.23	0.28	0.13	0.53	0.11	0.59	0.12	0.67
CS	Sand	0.24	0.25	0.25	0.36	0.14	0.59	0.12	0.61	0.13	0.61	0.25	0.26	0.15	0.49	0.13	0.56	0.12	0.64
	None	0.22	0.49	0.14	0.52	0.15	0.59	0.13	0.70	0.12	0.68	0.15	0.43	0.12	0.59	0.13	0.70	0.10	0.79
	All	0.16	0.53	0.11	0.59	0.11	0.66	0.10	0.73	0.10	0.72	0.13	0.47	0.12	0.65	0.09	0.77	0.07	0.85
	Clay	0.14	0.57	0.11	0.61	0.11	0.64	0.09	0.75	0.10	0.71	0.11	0.45	0.10	0.69	0.07	0.83	0.04	0.88
	Silt	0.19	0.49	0.13	0.58	0.14	0.63	0.10	0.69	0.12	0.66	0.14	0.41	0.14	0.66	0.11	0.75	0.08	0.86
Sand	0.22	0.46	0.12	0.55	0.14	0.61	0.12	0.64	0.11	0.69	0.14	0.43	0.13	0.62	0.11	0.69	0.11	0.82	

NS: non-stratified, SL: sandy loam, L: loam, SiL: silt loam, SiCL, CL: combination of silty clay loam (SiCL) and clay loam

Data Availability

Data will be made available on request.

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